

TYPOLOGICAL APPROACH TO TEACHING QUALITY LEVELS OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE GROUPS

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Abstract. *The typological approach is a valuable tool for teaching the Uzbek language to foreign learners. By understanding the typological features of the Uzbek language, learners can develop a deeper understanding of the language and how it works. This can help them to achieve greater proficiency in the language.*

Keywords: *typological approach, teaching Uzbek, L2, proficiency, learners, challenges.*

The Uzbek language is a Turkic language spoken by over 30 million people in Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, and Russia. It is the official language of Uzbekistan and is closely related to other Turkic languages such as Uyghur, Turkish, and Kazakh. The Uzbek language is a complex language with a rich history and culture. It has been influenced by several other languages, including Arabic, Persian, and Russian. This has resulted in a language that is both unique and challenging to learn. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the Uzbek language among foreign learners. This is due in part to the growing economic and political importance of Uzbekistan. Additionally, there is a growing interest in Uzbek culture and history. However, teaching the Uzbek language to foreign learners can be challenging. This is due to the complexity of the language and the lack of resources available. One approach to teaching the Uzbek language to foreign learners is the typological approach. This approach focuses on the typological features of the Uzbek language and how they differ from the typological features of the learner's native language. The typological approach is an effective way to teach the Uzbek language to foreign learners. This is because it helps learners to understand the underlying structure of the language and how it works. In addition, the typological approach can be used to teach the Uzbek language at all levels of proficiency. This makes it a versatile approach that can be used to meet the needs of a variety of learners. Language education is well recognized to entail the learning of a specific quantity of information at each stage of school. Language materials, consisting of phonetic, lexical, and grammatical information specified in the curriculum, serve as the foundation for the knowledge to be acquired, and they are distributed separately for each stage of education following the requirements of the state educational standard. Students build speaking abilities based on this information during the educational process. The development of speaking abilities in oral communication is the foundation of the communicative objective, since the capacity to share information in a second language, to communicate orally and in writing, is developed via listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. In Uzbek language classes, electronic manuals, videos, animations, texts, and audiovisuals (recorded sound, music, etc.) can be utilized. The employment of these strategies in native language and literary courses leads to a better understanding of the educational subject. Over time, an intimate bond develops between the teacher and the student. Many teaching approaches are used in educational processes such as single, double, group, and large groups. One of the linguistics Ken Robinson claimed that “education systems should recognize that “the greatest learning happens in groups”, because “collaboration is the stuff of growth”. That is to communicate in any language learners need to

have a conversation with each other. So, language classes should be a natural place to utilize cooperative learning strategies. When students work in groups, they improve their success, retention of information, and social interactions, as well as their self-confidence. It can alleviate the burden of contributing to a whole-class situation and allow students to work at their own speed. Moreover, working in pairs or small groups, the chain, press conferences, brainstorming, team games, assignments, linguistic games, puzzles, crosswords, roleplaying and simulation games, case studies, project technology, the tandem method, interactive tours, quests and web-quests, literature and musical compositions, discussions, multimedia and Internet technologies, podcasts, edutainment technology, critical thinking development, reciter contests, and literary conferences and various Uzbek festival speeches create an opportunity for learners at their own pace. These sorts of work are universal since they relate to multiple levels of learning and may be used to improve social, cultural, and scientific communication abilities. Teachers may create a friendly environment in which communication, design, problem-solving, and teamwork skills and capabilities can be developed. Furthermore, teaching Uzbek depending on its culture is one of the best ways to master the language as it motivates teachers to teach many parts of Uzbek culture to overseas pupils, reflects the learner’s interest in Uzbekistan, as well as the lifestyle of native speakers, and generates circumstances for becoming proficient in Uzbek in its cumulative function. Additionally, students can learn about social and cultural differences or issues, customs and traditions, national, local, and religious holidays, characters of native speakers, national dishes, and other topics that can help students develop cultural awareness and learn how to build bridges through intercultural dialogue. While discussing target-language teaching or learning, it should be stressed that we cannot envisage our daily class without computer technology. Using new learning tools, such as digital technologies that play an essential part in modern life and support the learning process, is one of the best and fastest ways for non-philology students to become proficient in Uzbek.

The typological approach is a valuable tool for teaching the Uzbek language to foreign learners. By understanding the typological features of the Uzbek language, learners can develop a deeper understanding of the language and how it works. This can help them to achieve greater proficiency in the language. By focusing on the typological characteristics of the Uzbek language, learners gain a deeper understanding of the language's fundamental structure and how its components interact. This contrasts with traditional approaches that emphasize rote memorization and grammar rules without explaining the underlying logic. The comparative nature of the typological approach allows learners to draw parallels between the Uzbek language and their native tongue or previously learned languages. This cross-linguistic comparison facilitates the transfer of knowledge and skills, making language learning more efficient. The typological approach can be effectively applied at all stages of language proficiency, from beginner to advanced levels. It provides a framework for understanding language development and can be tailored to the specific needs of learners at different stages of their language journey.

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